

Security of Information Resources and Preservation Issues in Federal University Libraries in South-Eastern Nigeria

Nzewi, Adaeze Nwona PhD (CLN)

Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Nnewi Campus

Urhiewhu, Lucky Oghenetega PhD

Dennis Osadebay University Asaba

lucky.urhiewhu@dou.edu.ng

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Abstract

The researcher examined “Security of Information Resources and Preservation Issues in University Libraries, Nigeria. The study formulated and tested two research questions. This study adopted the survey research design. The population of this study was 395 staff working in libraries of federal universities in South East Nigeria. The sample for the survey is 395, which corresponds to the population. The instrument used for data collection is a rating scale titled Security and Preservation of Information Resources in University Libraries (SPIRUL). The research questions were answered using mean and standard deviation. Some of the significant findings of the study are: the security threats to information resources in libraries are theft, vandalism, mutilation, fire hazards, natural disasters, cybercrime, non-return of borrowed materials, virus/worm attacks, web hacking, and illegal borrowing; poor roofing of the library, selfishness, ineffective disciplinary measures, and lack of modern security facilities. The researcher recommended that library authorities and staff should ensure that they work hand in hand to minimise security threats, such as theft and mutilation of information resources in the libraries, while also making requests to the school authorities for extra help in curbing other security threats the extent of preservation of information resources is high and needs to be sustained.

Keywords: Security, Preservation, Challenges, Information Resources, Issues, University and libraries

Introduction

Information resources in our university libraries should be preserved because of the importance of their information. Also, in a developing country like Nigeria, there is a dearth of valuable publications as it often takes a long time to purchase information resources from other countries due to the high exchange rate of our local currency compared to dollars and pounds. In addition, low financial allocations are made available to university libraries. These resources

are inadequate, and they could be expensive to reproduce. Therefore, the preservation of these information resources cannot be over-emphasized. According to Aina, as cited in Ogbodo (2010), preservation is a means of taking care of library materials to avoid deterioration. Many factors pose threats to information resources that may attack or destroy them. These include climatic conditions such as humidity, aridity and ultraviolet rays; biological agents such as bookworms, ants, and rodents; and natural hazards such as fire, flood and war. English

Folkdance and Songs Society (2009) define preservation as the totality of measures for maintaining the integrity of documents and their information. It includes all the managerial and financial considerations, storage and accommodation provisions, techniques and methods for safeguarding documentary materials.

Great literature, art, and science works must be preserved and accessible to future learners. Libraries preserve objects through careful storage procedures, policies of borrowing and use, and repair and maintenance as needed. Libraries are physical manifestations of the values of an entity. Libraries serve a cultural role in preserving personal, organisational and a nation's memories. Great literature, art, and science works are preserved and accessible to future learners. Kalis (2015) stated that preserving and conserving library resources aid better services, so it is deemed necessary considering future generations of users. Njeze's (2012) study revealed that the most commonly used techniques in preserving and conserving library materials in their libraries are binding, photocopying, shelving books for free air flow, adequate security, cleaning and dusting.

On the other hand, library collections are changing rapidly as more and more electronic resources become available. The proliferation of electronic resources does not mean that printed resources will disappear. Library resources and materials must be safe. Hence, libraries must make security devices available to ensure the materials are not stolen or mutilated. Security can have a variety of connotations in the library world. Internet security and security of library materials are both important aspects of library services, but more important is the safety of library collections, patrons and staff (Agboola & Aduku, 2019). Security is the state of being free from danger or risk, in which an entity or organisation is protected against espionage or attack (Ochogwu & Abdulrahman, 2018). In other words, Edonu (2017) defines security as various measures or policies to ensure information materials' integrity, authenticity, and longevity. These information materials appear in different formats, such as print and non-print (electronic, online, and audiovisual, to mention but a few).

Expressing security as a concern to libraries, Olajide (2017) argues that libraries are 'systems' and security is vital to maintaining balance. It aids in adopting strategies for librarians and other staff to prevent or ameliorate the negative consequences of a realised threat in the libraries. Therefore, library security management is a professional effort to deal practically with knotty problems of library safety and security. The typical library security outfit protects users and their properties, as well as library collections, computers, and other systems. Maintaining security is necessary for every establishment; therefore, staff must know how to handle safety-related situations consistently. Librarians need to devise a very concrete and physical means of securing the materials available in the library and to have telecommunications or electronic security systems that will help to provide a safe and secure facility for library resources and equipment.

This study provides an opportunity for surveying the security and preservation of information resources in university libraries for optimal use of the library because libraries are social institutions created to conserve knowledge, preserve cultural heritage, and provide information aid for research and recreation (Aguolu & Aguolu in Ogbodo, 2010). The above objectives of the library cannot be met if librarians allow the information resource in their custody to be mutilated, stolen or deteriorated. Therefore, as information professionals, librarians have a mandate – to explore ways of securing, managing and preventing library and information materials from infringement and to ensure their continued availability for as long as possible, remembering that prevention is better than cure. Based on this background, this paper on security and preservation issues in University libraries in Nigeria focuses on federal higher institutions in the East.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of this study was to examine security and preservation issues in University libraries in Nigeria focuses on federal higher institutions in the East, while the specifics were to:

1. Ascertain the extent to which information resources are preserved in libraries of federal universities in southeast Nigeria.
2. Identify the challenges faced in securing and preserving information resources in libraries of federal universities in Southeast Nigeria.

Literature Review

Information Resource Security

The concept of security is broad in scope and coverage. This has given rise to different definitions of security. Some of these definitions include defending information and information-bearing materials from unauthorised access, use, disclosure, disruption, modification, perusal, inspection, recording or destruction. (Omosekejimi, Ijiekhuamlen & Oyeme, 2015). Confidentiality implies that the resources are only available to authorised users, and integrity means that the collection or information is not altered but is accurate and complete. Availability refers to making sure that authorised users have reliable and timely access to the collection at the time they need it.

According to Edem (2010), security is an assurance of future well-being and freedom from threat. It is how policies, programming, procedures or measures are deployed to mitigate risk and ensure access to a particular resource feared to disappear. On the other hand, Ani (2010) defines security as being physically, emotionally, and psychologically protected from other harmful attacks and terror, which could be seen as non-desirable. Security of information resources has to do with the provision, maintenance and protection of books and non-book materials in order to ensure longevity, accessibility and availability of materials to library users. However, university libraries are prone to various degrees of security threats, which could be grouped into general security threats and emerging security threats.

Heads of academic libraries have been battling with security challenges in their various libraries and have also made several attempts to address the security issues that relate to vandalism, theft and mutilation of library materials, using the traditional (manual) methods, but with limited success (Osayande, 2019). It was averred by

Uzuegbu and Okoro (2012) that different libraries had put various measures in place, ranging from employing more security personnel to formulating security policies to alleviate the wanton destruction of library materials by rough users. However, library materials are still being stolen and defaced regularly. Prior literature has revealed limited studies on using modern technologies (ICT) in securing library materials (Ogboniyomi, 2011). ICT has proven to be the solution to curbing security issues in academic libraries, as manual methods have not been able to curb the menace. In developed countries, modern technologies have been installed and deployed in academic libraries to help secure library collections and monitor the activities of patrons and even library employees. Securing and protecting the collection of libraries can help provide an effective service to the community. In some cases, the security of stocks is not viewed as a significant issue until librarian's audit stocks and realize that many collections cannot be accounted for. Academic libraries in Nigeria can adopt integrated alarm security systems that consist of security sensors or detectors, gate-entering alarms, perimeter protection defence, video record linkage, and network alarm reports (Ukata, 2018).

Preservation of Information Resources

Preservation constitutes all the activities to ensure that information resources maintain quality in formats and contents. Preservation has been defined by Popoola, as cited in Oluwaniyi (2015), as everything that adds to the physical well-being of information resources, such as the protection, maintenance, and restoration of library and archive information resources. The term preservation also has to do with managerial and financial responsibilities of the library, such as storage, accommodation, staffing, policies, techniques and methods involved in protecting library and archives information resources and the information it contains. Preservation is part of library management, which ensures that information resources in any format are easily accessible and useable as long as they are wanted.

In preservation, consideration is given to every element that promotes the protection of the materials, including the housing, storage system,

and security against threats such as theft, mutilation, and poor handling. Therefore, preservation is a more embracing concept, including conservation (Ogunmodede & Ebijuwa, 2013). Oluwaniyi (2015) states that preservation safeguards library information resources from decay and deterioration, which aligns with the above statement. Preservation is the process by which all measures are taken to control and retard the deterioration of information resources in the library. Murray, as cited in Asuzu (2018), explains that preservation is an indirect method of treatment in which the environment around an item is changed. This includes stabilizing, maintaining and monitoring temperature, humidity, light exposure, air pollution, dust, and mould. Preservation also includes surveying the proper storage and handling techniques, security, including theft, vandalism, disaster prevention, education, training and outreach programs for staff, patrons, clients and the public.

According to Alex-Nmecha and Okoro (2020), preservation is the measure taken before damage is done to information resources. Activities currently defining the realm of preservation of library materials include conservation (general collections repair and unique collection), reformatting (microfilming, photocopying and digitalisation) selection for preservation, environmental monitoring and control, care and handling of materials disaster preparedness and

recovery, standards relating to materials, practice and techniques commercial binding, and preservation education and training (Njeze, 2012). Preservation was further described by Jordan, as cited in Asuzu (2018), as a term for an array of activities, principles, practices, and organisations that ensure the usability, longevity, and accessibility of recorded knowledge, while San (2019) puts it as the task of minimizing or reducing the physical and chemical deterioration of documents.

Methodology

The researcher examined security and preservation issues in Nigerian university libraries. This study adopted the survey research design. The population of this study was 395 staff working in libraries of federal universities in South East Nigeria. The sample for the study is 395, which corresponds to the population. The instrument used for data collection is a rating scale titled Security and Preservation of Information Resources in University Libraries (SPIRULQ). The research questions were answered using mean and standard deviation.

Results of Data Analysis

Research Question One: What are the security threats to information resources in libraries of federal universities in the South-East geopolitical zone, Nigeria?

Table 1: Item-by-Item Means and Standard Deviation of the Security Threats to Information Resources in Libraries of Federal Universities

s/n	Security threats	\bar{X}	Std	Remark
1.	Theft	3.77	0.59	SA
2.	Vandalism	3.09	0.79	A
3.	Mutilation	2.80	0.86	A
4.	Fire Hazards	2.68	0.88	A
5.	Natural Disasters	2.76	0.80	A
6.	Cybercrime	2.63	0.87	A
7.	Non-return of borrowed materials	2.95	0.80	A
8.	Virus/worm attacks	3.10	0.77	A
9.	Web Hacking	2.91	0.81	A
10.	Illegal borrowing	2.81	0.84	A
		29.51	3.85	

To answer research question one, item-by-item mean and standard deviation were employed, with strongly agree to disagree responses. Table 1 shows that through item-by-item mean analysis, all the items, except item 1, are accepted as security threats to information resources in libraries of federal universities. The mean responses for the items are approximately 3.00, indicating agreement (Ag) with the item statements, while the mean response for item 1 (that is, “theft”) is approximately 4, indicating substantial agreement with the item statement.

This shows that all the item statements in the table are security threats to library information resources. The observed cluster mean score of 29.51 is greater than the expected mean of 25. The standard deviation of the individual scores is 3.85.

Research Question 2: What challenges are faced in securing and preserving information resources in libraries of federal universities in the South East geopolitical zone, Nigeria?

Table 11: Item-by-Item Means and Standard Deviation of the Challenges Faced in Securing and Preserving Information Resources

s/n	Challenges	\bar{X}	Std	Remark
1.	Lack of policy	3.06	0.76	Ag
2.	Inadequate funding	3.07	0.77	Ag
3.	Insufficient equipment	2.91	0.79	Ag
4.	Tropical climate	2.87	0.82	Ag
5.	Non-permanent library security staff	2.97	0.80	Ag
6.	Non-possession of necessary skills by library staff	2.99	0.76	Ag
7.	Hardware and software breakdown	3.03	0.81	Ag
8.	Indifference on the part of library staff	3.41	0.58	Ag
9.	Inadequate library staff.	2.87	0.82	Ag
		27.19	2.60	

To answer research question 2, item-by-item mean and standard deviation have been employed with strongly agree to disagree responses. The table shows that the challenges to securing and preserving library information resources are listed through item-by-item mean analysis. The respondents agreed that item statements are challenges to securing and preserving. These items have mean response scores of approximately 3, indicating that the library staff agree (A) with the item statements.

Discussion of Findings

Security Threats to Information Resources in Libraries in Federal Universities

Table 1 of this report presents the security threats to library information resources: theft, vandalism, mutilation, fire hazards, natural disasters, cybercrime, non-return of borrowed materials, virus/worm attacks, web hacking, and illegal borrowing. The statistical test showed that the respondents' mean rating score for security

threats to information resources in libraries of federal universities was significant. This shows that many factors pose a security threat to information resources in libraries in federal universities. This means that information resources in those libraries will often be destroyed, which may lead to a shortage. This is in line with the findings of Ugochukwu (2021), who found that information resources are prone to various crimes such as theft, mutilation, cybercrime, etc.

Challenges to Securing Information Resources in Libraries

The study's findings revealed several challenges in securing library information resources. Some of the challenges revealed by the findings are challenges faced in preserving and securing information resources in the libraries are lack of policy, inadequate funding, insufficient equipment, tropical climate, non-permanent library security staff, non-possession of necessary

skills by library staff, hardware and software breakdown, indifference on the part of library staff, inadequate library staff. These challenges make it difficult, if not impossible, for the information resources to be secured and, as a result, expose the information resources to more security threats. These findings align with Urhiewhu, Emojorho, and Omah (2018), who found many challenges in securing library information resources.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The study investigated security and preservation issues in University libraries in Nigeria. Two research questions were formulated to guide the study. The researcher reviewed some related literature under the subheadings, including significant concepts such as security and preservation of information resources, materials vulnerable to security breaches, cause of security threats in libraries, measures to secure library materials, and preservation methods adopted in libraries. Having analysed and presented data, the researcher concludes that various security threats exist to library information resources. Some security threats are theft, vandalism, mutilation, fire hazards, natural disasters, cybercrime, non-return of borrowed materials, virus/worm attacks, web hacking, and illegal borrowing. Hence, if information resources are to be preserved, they must be secured against threats.

Based on the results of this research work, the following recommendations were made: The library authorities and staff should ensure that they work hand in hand to minimise security threats such as theft and mutilation of information resources in the libraries, while also making requests to the school authorities for extra help in curbing other security threats; The extent of preservation of information resources is high and needs to be sustained.

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